

Annex D.2 – Data on presumptive ESBL-, AmpC- and/or carbapenemase-producing microorganisms and their resistance occurrence (routine and specific monitoring)

Annex to:

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D.2.1. ESBL-, AmpC-, ESBL+AmpC- and CP-phenotypes

Reporting countries determined the susceptibility of *Salmonella* spp. and indicator *E. coli* to selected antimicrobials belonging to different classes (Panel 1) according to Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2020/1729. Isolates resistant to cefotaxime, ceftazidime and/or meropenem after susceptibility testing with Panel 1, were further tested with a second panel of different beta-lactam antimicrobials, including different cephalosporins and carbapenems (Panel 2). Testing the isolates using Panel 2 facilitated the phenotypic identification of presumptive ESBL-, AmpC- and/or CP-producers. All isolates identified in the specific monitoring of ESBL-/AmpC-/CP-producing *E. coli* and the specific monitoring of CP-producing *E. coli* were susceptibility tested using both Panel 1 and Panel 2. Also, whole genome sequencing (WGS) has been authorised as an alternative method for phenotypic testing of *Salmonella* spp. and *E. coli* displaying resistance to extended-spectrum cephalosporins or carbapenems. Detailed information is provided in Appendix A – Materials and methods.

For this report, the categorisation of isolates displaying extended-spectrum cephalosporin- or carbapenem resistance as presumptive ESBL-, AmpC- or CP-producers was done based on the EUCAST guidelines for detection of resistance mechanisms and specific resistances of clinical and/or epidemiological importance (EUCAST, 2017) and the knowledge of consulted experts. Five main categorisations of phenotypes were used; 1. ESBL; 2. AmpC; 3. ESBL + AmpC; 4 CP and 5. Other. A figure displaying the phenotypes inferred based on the resistance to the beta-lactams included in Panel 2 is shown in Appendix A, Materials and Methods.

D.2.2. ESBL-/AmpC-producers prevalence maps

The prevalence of presumptive ESBL- and/or AmpC-producing *E. coli* in samples from food-producing animals and meat from retail varied markedly between MSs (Chapter 5). These variations were also evident when assessing the occurrence of isolates with ESBL- or AmpC phenotypes separately (Figure 1, Figure 2, Figure 3 and Figure 4).

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 1: Spatial distribution of the prevalence of presumptive ESBL-producing *Escherichia coli* from (a) meat from pigs in 2023, (b) meat from bovines in 2023, (c) meat from broilers in 2022 and (d) meat from turkeys in 2022, EU MSs and non-MSs. The designation of Kosovo is without prejudice to positions on status and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2: Spatial distribution of the prevalence of presumptive ESBL-producing *Escherichia coli* from (a) fattening pigs in 2023, (b) cattle under 1 year of age in 2023, (c) broilers in 2022 and (d) fattening turkeys in 2022, EU MSs and non-MSs. The designation of Kosovo is without prejudice to positions on status and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3: Spatial distribution of the prevalence of presumptive AmpC-producing *Escherichia coli* from (a) meat from pigs in 2023, (b) meat from bovines in 2023, (c) meat from broilers in 2022 and (d) meat from turkeys in 2022, EU MSs and non-MSs. The designation of Kosovo is without prejudice to positions on status and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4: Spatial distribution of the prevalence of presumptive AmpC-producing *Escherichia coli* from (a) fattening pigs in 2023, (b) cattle under 1 year of age in 2023, (c) broilers in 2022 and (d) fattening turkeys in 2022, EU MSs and non-MSs. The designation of Kosovo is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

D.2.3. Key outcome indicator of prevalence of ESBL- and/or AmpC-producing *Escherichia coli* in food-producing animals, 2014-2023

Table 1: Key outcome indicator of prevalence of ESBL- and/or AmpC-producing *Escherichia coli* in food-producing animals from 2014-2023, EU MSs and non-MSs.

Country	Period ^(a)								
	2014-2015	2015-2016	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019	2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023
Austria	52.1	52.1	60.6	57.0	56.2	52.8	54.0	52.1	53.2
Belgium	58.2	65.7	71.9	68.1	55.6	56.0	49.0	48.0	47.5
Bulgaria	58.8	64.3	55.3	51.9	55.7	52.2	37.9	42.1	45.2
Croatia	33.1	38.8	46.7	48.1	60.6	58.7	60.5	62.8	42.7
Cyprus	6.8	23.9	19.5	7.5	8.5	7.5	27.0	20.8	11.7
Czechia	30.8	40.5	42.1	37.6	38.0	34.6	36.0	36.9	40.4
Denmark	29.1	28.3	24.0	24.0	26.0	25.2	19.0	19.0	14.1
Estonia	36.8	36.7	35.3	38.2	50.5	48.7	32.6	33.0	19.5
Finland	4.1	6.3	6.3	6.2	6.2	1.7	4.3	4.7	4.4
France	39.4	39.6	32.6	26.4	22.1	16.9	10.1	9.9	11.0
Germany	46.2	46.8	47.4	47.0	48.9	46.9	42.8	43.5	52.6
Greece	32.8	54.3	59.1	42.4	42.5	47.4	45.7	35.1	45.7
Hungary	59.0	60.6	67.5	65.8	63.4	53.7	54.3	61.2	53.3
Iceland	0	3.1	5.3	4.0	6.4	6.5	2.0	1.7	0.7
Ireland	29.0	42.3	47.6	40.1	45.7	36.1	32.1	30.6	28.3
Italy		90.0	88.7	82.3	82.4	68.7	65.1	65.3	72.9
Latvia	48.7	62.3	60.6	43.6	48.8	51.0	48.1	45.1	49.8
Lithuania	17.9	49.7	67.9	69.3	55.8	51.8	59.2	47.4	44.2
Luxembourg		52.6	40.9	40.7	52.4	52.2	42.5	41.8	21.3
Malta	0	0	17.9	45.7	66.9	67.2	52.1	34.2	35.0
Netherlands	19.8	25.1	23.2	18.4	14.4	12.1	16.4	17.5	21.0
Norway		10.6	12.8	9.4	12.7	12.4	9.3	9.2	12.2
Poland	36.7	37.1	43.5	44.5	41.9	34.0	29.7	35.6	41.1
Portugal	70.1	61.3	56.5	71.4	77.6	65.4	50.8	48.8	59.6
Romania	55.6	60.8	65.6	66.0	69.4	66.4	65.9	70.7	72.9
Slovakia	44.3	62.1	66.7	34.9	38.9	72.3	76.7	71.4	74.2
Slovenia	29.1	71.6	79.0	72.2	75.5	67.5	66.4	51.2	49.4
Spain	85.3	86.4	85.7	85.7	79.0	73.1	73.0	71.3	70.5
Sweden	17.8	20.7	22.0	12.3	13.2	12.1	9.2	6.3	1.6
Switzerland	25.0	30.4	25.1	21.1	19.6	14.3	8.3	7.0	4.1
United Kingdom		0	0	0	0	0	0		

^(a)Proportions (in percent) of samples from broilers, fattening turkeys, fattening pigs and cattle under 1 year weighted by population correction unit that are identified as positive for presumptive ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* in the framework of the specific monitoring of ESBL-/AmpC-/CP-producing *E. coli* (2020/1729/EU).

D.2.4 ESBL-, AmpC- and CP-encoding genes identified during the specific monitoring of ESBL-, AmpC-, and/or CP-producing *E. coli* and the specific monitoring of CP-producing *E. coli* isolates using whole genome sequencing

In 2022, six MSs (Czechia, Germany, Finland, Italy, the Netherlands and Sweden) and one non-MS (Norway) reported WGS data. Further, eight MSs (Austria, Belgium, Czechia, Germany, Finland, Italy, the Netherlands and Sweden), the United Kingdom (Northern Ireland) and one non-MS (Norway) reported WGS data in 2023.

A variety of ESBL-encoding genes were detected in all countries reporting WGS data (Tables Annex D3). Overall, the most commonly reported ESBL-encoding gene was *bla*_{CTX-M-1}. In 2022, it was reported in broilers (n=164), fattening turkeys (n=51), retail meat from broilers (n=106) and retail meat from turkeys (n=41). Further, *bla*_{CTX-M-1} was detected in fattening pigs (n=424), cattle under 1 year of age (n=301), retail meat from pigs (n=42) and retail meat from bovines in 2023 (n=35). In poultry, *bla*_{SHV-12} was the second most frequently reported ESBL-encoding gene overall, and in retail meat from broilers and fattening turkeys, it was reported more frequently than *bla*_{CTX-M-1}. The *bla*_{SHV-12} gene was detected in all poultry matrices, namely broilers (n=141), fattening turkeys (n=63), retail meat from broilers (n=109) and retail meat from turkeys (n=32). In fattening pigs, cattle under one year and meat derived thereof, *bla*_{CTX-M-15} was the second most frequently reported ESBL-encoding gene. It was reported in 66 isolates from fattening pigs and 277 isolates from cattle under one year. Notably, its occurrence in meat was lower, with six isolates from meat from pigs and 17 isolates from meat from bovines harbouring *bla*_{CTX-M-15} in 2023.

Seven different plasmid-mediated AmpC-encoding genes were reported in 2022 and 2023 (Tables Annex D3). These included *bla*_{CFE-1} (fattening pigs, retail meat from pigs, cattle under 1 year of age, and retail meat from bovines), *bla*_{CMY-2} (all matrices), *bla*_{CMY-101} (broilers, cattle under 1 year of age, retail meat from broilers and retail meat from turkeys), *bla*_{CMY-102} (broilers, fattening pigs and cattle under 1 year of age,), *bla*_{CMY-113} (broilers and retail meat from turkeys), *bla*_{CMY-155} (retail meat from broilers, fattening turkeys, retail meat from turkeys and fattening pigs), and *bla*_{DHA-1} (fattening pigs and cattle under 1 year of age). Overall, *bla*_{CMY-2} was the most commonly reported plasmid-mediated AmpC-encoding gene. Chromosomal mutations resulting in an AmpC phenotype were also commonly reported. In fattening turkeys, fattening pigs, cattle under 1 year and meat derived thereof, the C-42T mutation was the most common genetic determinant for the AmpC phenotype, while *bla*_{CMY-2} was the most common AmpC-encoding gene in broilers and meat from broilers.

In the CP-specific monitoring, one CP-encoding gene was reported in 2022, and two different genes in 2023 (Tables Annex D3). In 2022, the *bla*_{OXA-181} gene was reported from fattening turkeys (n=1). In 2023, the *bla*_{OXA-181} gene was most frequently reported, detected in fattening pigs (n=19) and in cattle under 1 year of age (n=4), all from Italy. Further, the *bla*_{NDM-5} gene was detected in five isolates from fattening pigs in Czechia. CP-encoding genes were also reported from a single indicator commensal *E. coli* isolate from fattening turkeys in 2022, and from for isolates recovered in the specific monitoring of ESBL-/AmpC-/CP-producing *E. coli* in 2022 and 2023. The details are presented in Section 5.5 Monitoring carbapenemase-producing *Escherichia coli*.

Some countries reported both genotypic and phenotypic data in the routine monitoring of indicator commensal *E. coli*, the specific monitoring of ESBL-/AmpC-/CP-producing *E. coli*

and in the specific monitoring of CP-producing *E. coli*. These data are also presented in Annex D.3 in a separate excel sheet showing the correspondence between phenotype according to MIC values and phenotype predicted by genotype (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14645440>).